

Muslim Women and Hijab : A Study into the Subjects of Female Identities, Empowerment, and Body Image

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Introduction: The Islamic practice of covering is referred to the Arabic word Hijab rather than “Veil,” as it is the proper phrase to describe such a practice, which translates as “Covering.” As the term “Hijab” is quite interpretive, there is a wide range of clothing options, from simple headscarves to burqas that enclose the body and face. It addresses more than dress guidelines; it also addresses moral limits and respect for women. It is a component of modest behaviour and neighborhood harmony. Hijab and the term scarf are now used interchangeably. The concept is occasionally expanded to include cultural clothing codes like the chador of Iran, the Shalwar Kamij of Pakistan, and the burqa of Afghanistan and Kashmir. The term veil or Hijab, however, has been transformed into a contentious issue in discussions in the Muslim world by Western media. The media illustrates inequity by making many arguments defensive and presenting women as victims. To be clear, a Muslim refers to someone who adheres to and practices the Islam faith, centred on the principles of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) and the sacred text, the Quran. Surat-un-Nur 24:30–31, one of the four ayahs in the Holy Quran that mentions the veil, is adequate to bolster the argument.

Furthermore, tell the believing women to lower their gaze and be modest, and to display their adornment only that which is apparent, and to draw their veils over their bosoms, and not to reveal their adornment save to their own husbands or fathers or husbands fathers, or their sons or their husbands’ sons, or their brothers or their brothers’ sons or sisters sons, or their women, or their slaves, or male attendants who lack vigour, or children who know nought of women’s nakedness. And let them not stamp their feet to reveal what they hide of their adornment. And turn unto Allah together, O believers, in order that ye may succeed. (Surat-un-Nur 24:30–31)

Islam did not concoct the practice of veiling women. Long before the birth of the Islamic Prophet Muhammad, people began to wear veils. Veiling was a prac-

tice in near and Middle Eastern societies such as the Byzantines, Sassanids, and others. (Fadwa)

Concept of Veil: A Historical Prospective

Hijab is an Islamic notion of decency and privacy. This idea is not exclusive to Islam but is inherited by other religions such as Judaism, where the concept of modesty is known as Tzuniut and Christianity. The Islamic notion of the Hijab is most commonly reflected in women's clothes. Hijab garments range from basic head scarves (khimaar or simply Hijab) to full-body cloaks such as abayas, and burqas centred on the principles of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) and the sacred text, the Quran. Surat-un-Nur 24:30–31, one of the four ayahs in the Holy Quran that mentions the veil, is adequate to bolster the argument.

Veiling's historical origins in Western Europe can be traced back to the Byzantine Empire, where veiling codes ascribed a high social standing to families whose women were veiled. Married women in the Middle Ages were expected to conceal their tresses with different coverings. Paintings of metropolitan women in Western Europe frequently show everything concealed except the face and hands. Peasant and working-class women who did not cover were deemed "loose" and open to attack at the time. Throughout history, the hijab has been donned for a multitude of reasons, including but not limited to economic, social, gender, religious, and political factors (Kandiyoti, 1987). The discourse encompassing the hijab is not a product of its own accord. According to historical sources, there is evidence to suggest that discussions surrounding the hijab were present in pre-Islamic Arabia. According to Homa Hoodfar (1993) during that time, the hijab "was a sign of status and was practiced by the elites" (p. 6)

The first documented case of women veiling or concealing their hair is found in Assyrian law documents dating from the 13th century BC. Aristocratic ladies only used it. Covering one's hair/head was prohibited for prostitutes, enslaved people, and impoverished women. There is proof that ladies wore varying degrees of head coverings in both the Greek and Roman regimes. Head coverings have been linked with worship and dedication, particularly in Rome. While in Greece, evidence from art and ceramics from the period suggests that dignified women covered their hair outside the house. We can be confident that women's head or hair covering was not uncommon even as our views about the extent and motivations for covering wax wane as new information comes to light.

The Valmiki Ramayana is regarded as a source of theology by adherents of Hinduism. According to this scripture, after the Lankan triumph, when Sitaji was brought to Rama by Vibhishan from Ashok Vatika, Rama grew enraged at the attempts to clear the crowd of Sita's devotees and shouted the following:

व्यसनेषु न कृच्छ्रेषु न युद्धेषु स्वयंवरो।
न क्रतौ नो विवाहे वा दर्शनं दूष्यते स्त्रियाः

(In times of adversity, on the occasions of physical or mental suffering, in war, in self-interest, in marriage, the presence of women in Yajna appearing to

others is not a matter of blame.)

According to the Holy text, presenting as a lady to strangers is unlawful in normal circumstances. After Ravan died, Queen Mandodari and other queens rushed to the battlefield to observe a moment of silence. The veil was also there at that time. As said by Maharani Mandodari

दृष्ट्या न खल्वभिक्रुद्धो मामिहानवगुण्डिताम्।
निर्गतां नगरद्वारात् पद्भ्यामेवागतां प्रभो॥

(O Lord, today I do not have a veil on my face. I have come here on foot from the city gate. Why do not you get angry by seeing me in this condition?)

In addition, it is mentioned in the Rig Veda: “When Brahma has made you a woman, you should lower your gaze and not look up. You should put your feet together, and you should not reveal what the garment and the veil conceal.”

Women are objectified and restricted to a specific appearance in many countries. They frequently receive comments and criticism over their clothes. Because of their clothes, they are targeted for hatred and violence. Unfortunately, women confront misconceptions regarding their religious headwear and dress. In such cases, the Hijab separates Muslim women from their peers by removing the stigma associated with a distinctive appearance that defines them. It represents that women, regardless of what they wear, need to be treated with dignity and respect. When women come out in society, displaying their beauty, they experience a feeling of pride because they represent the ladies of the entire globe.

Female Identities, Empowerment and Body Image

In contemporary Islam, there are multiple reasons for wearing the hijab. Many Muslim women who wear the hijab perceive it as a symbol of chastity and dignity (Bullock, 2002). For others, as Moghadam (1994) indicates, “Veiling becomes not only a cultural symbol and an assertion of identity but a matter of convenience—it allows women physical mobility in public spaces, free from the gaze and harassment of men and the disapproval of family members” (p. 20). The goal of the hijab, according to Islamic doctrine, is not to are bound women or to indicate women’s subordination; instead, it’s intended supposed to be worn as safeguard from male gaze and to prevent being assessed based on looks. Some Muslim women observe the hijab as nothing more than a religious symbol and a form of prayer. In recent years, the hijab has evolved from a cultural and traditional emblem to a form of protest against western rule.

In a globalised society, the imposition of Western culture’s dress code and lifestyle is causing many Muslim women to reinforce their Muslim identity by wearing globalised attires (Smith, 2004).

Hijab is the traditional clothing rule for Muslim women when they leave their homes. The Qur’an instructs Muslim women to wear Hijab because they should not exhibit their look (beauty) except what is already visible, such as their face, hands up to the wrist, and feet. Notably, clothing is an important social institution facilitating major ideological and nonverbal cues. (Bullock & Nesbitt-Larking, 2011 P.74)

Renowned Canadian sociologist Erving Goffman described social interaction as a form of theatre in which participants take on different roles, like performers on a stage. He describes the social behaviour of people as a performance, arguing that performance is “all the activity of a given participant on a given occasion which serves to influence in any way any of the other participants” (Goffman, 1959 P.15). He contends that when a person interacts with others, he or she tries to influence or control the perception that others may have of him. He or she accomplishes this by controlling the environment, demeanor, and looks. This implies that humans are continually communicating with others. One of the most significant stigmatizing signs for Muslim women has been the Hijab. Muslim women are easily identifiable due to the Hijab. Because Islam forbids them from removing it in public, they cannot escape this stigma, even for a short period of time.

The difficulty in defining Islamic identity is in not only defining it in terms of Western concepts but also in determining the implicit meaning of the term “person” in non-Western Islamic societies, in comparing and contrasting it with the Western concept of person, and in interpreting it in accordance with those comparisons and differences (Kippenberg et al., 1990 P.2). “Dangerous, scary, intriguing, threatening, intimidating, oppressive, irritating, aggressive, traditional, conservative and reactionary” are some of the adjectives commonly used in Europe concerning Hijab (Amiriaux, 2007). Western ethnocentrism, intolerance of other communities, the preservation of values and tradition, anti-immigrant prejudice, racism, and eroding universalism are the causes of the animosity for the veil in the West. The trend in Western society to restrict space for the veil reflects xenophobia; if a society is intolerant of immigrants in general, it is no surprise that the headscarf, as a sign of external presence, is despised, and Islamophobia is one of its manifestations. (Helbling, 2014). Due to the modern-day politicization of Islam, the growth of anti-Muslim sentiment, and prejudice founded in the perception that Muslim principles are incompatible with progressive Western values, Muslim women receive the most scrutiny for wearing a head covering. Accept that the Hijab is not only a religious sign that may be abolished under the pretence of secularism but an essential aspect of Muslim women’s dress that makes them feel vulnerable if ordered to be removed. It is unnecessary to begin stripping naked to feel confident and liberated. After all, didn’t man develop clothes and begin to wrap himself in luxurious fabrics to feel exalted and dignified? Taking off one’s garments would be tantamount to reverting humankind to the Stone Age.

The Hijab gives women a sense of positive reinforcement about their appearance. However, it also connotes a sense of neutrality because it does not directly influence their perception of their bodies favourably or adversely. Hijab may challenge Western perceptions of powerful or feminist women, yet it does not always conflict with Western principles of female empowerment and feminism. Western representations of empowered women tend to exploit women’s bodies by commercializing them, challenging Western beauty norms. In the United

States (US), one study reported that women who wore non-Western clothing with a hijab reported less pressure to adhere to and internalize the thin ideal than those who wore Western clothing without a hijab (Dunkel, Davidson, & Qurashi, 2010). The Hijab may also allow some Muslim women to oppose or reject normative norms of beauty, which can be perceived as empowering.

To protect women, Islam prescribes a Hijab. This in no way makes them weaker. Deciding to wear a Hijab has allowed me to express my distinct personality without succumbing to the demands of billion-dollar companies that exploit women (Ahmad). Wassyla Tamsali, an Algerian feminist, has challenged feminists to condemn “everything that reduces women to their reproductive sexuality and to their exclusive dependency on the community that decides their fate” and not to be deterred by religious justifications made in support of the Hijab. After all, the feminist campaign for abortion in the 1970s targeted a doctrine more essential to the Catholic Church than veiling has ever been to Islam ((Tamsali 2004). Furthermore, contemporary feminists should investigate how hijabi Muslim women may contribute to feminist movements in both the West and the East. Although historical and modern prejudices claimed that covering one’s body symbolized oppression, the study firmly asserted that wearing a Hijab makes them feel more emancipated from the male gaze. This does not imply that the Hijab is a cure for patriarchal restraints on women, but rather that it is at least as valid a source of freedom and liberation for some as displaying one’s body might be for others.

In 2004, France banned “clothes through which students conspicuously display their religious affiliation” in schools. In the following years, France became the first European country to outlaw the full-face veil in public places, followed by Belgium, Latvia, Bulgaria, Austria, Denmark, and various sections of Switzerland. At the same time, Muslim women are permitted to wear Hijab in many other European or Western nations, including the United Kingdom, Germany, the United States, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand.

In Tunisia, women were restricted from wearing Hijab in government jobs in 1981. In 1953, Egypt’s late President Gamal Abdel Nasser was not inclined to approve the Muslim Brotherhood’s leader’s demand that Muslim women wear Hijab. Indeed, it was not until the end of the twentieth century that Muslim women in Egypt began to wear Hijab again. The hijab is regarded by lots Muslims as a means of political and cultural defiance and a symbol of identity for Muslim women; “Identity is used here to refer to the individual definitions of self and personhood, and how the inner sense of self is connected to the outer perception of self” (Dei, 1997, p. 241). The media’s coverage of the hijab controversy has perpetuated a dichotomous perspective of “us versus them” and reinforced opposing viewpoints regarding the oppression of women who wear the hijab versus those who do not. Shahnaz Khan (2002) *Aversion and Desire negotiating Muslim Female identity in the Diaspora* suggested that the media is “strengthening the Orientalist view of the veil [hijab] as oppressive and the Islamist view of the veil as liberating” (p. 19).

Conclusion: The wearing of a Hijab by Muslim women causes no damage or difficulty to others. Because its usage is not harmful to the public interest, it should be seen as part of the freedom of religion given to all citizens by the constitution, which permits Muslim women to practise religion by the teachings of their faith. Refusing to comprehend, accept, and respect Muslim history and legacy, which makes the Hijab an essential manifestation of a Muslim woman's religious identity, can only foster extremism. When the terrible inclinations of prejudice and hatred are replaced with tolerance, mutual love, and understanding, Nigeria and the world will be better. (Daily trust). Dress is a matter of personal preference. It displays their individuality and helps them to feel their best. When Muslim women wear the Hijab, it gives them a feeling of identity, just like any other item of clothing. It assures them that they have a distinct identity. They want to be acknowledged for their faith and culture, distinguishing them from others. This encounter has boosted the confidence of many women.

A potential approach to combat sexism and racism involves promoting the notion of collective action among women as a means of advocating for their rights. The peaceful resolution of the misunderstanding surrounding Islamic religious clothing necessitates a collaborative effort between individuals of both Muslim and non-Muslim backgrounds level of cultural diversity, is to promote social cohesion and integration among its citizens. The effective approach towards managing the population of immigrants from diverse regions, including those with a significant Muslim demographic, is to implement policies that foster unity rather than division.

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